

DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF VALUES IN PREPARING STUDENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *In today's era of globalization, consistent scientific research is being conducted in the world higher education system on professional socialization of students, development of moral-ethical and ideological competence, improvement of methods of education of social activity and initiative, development of ideological immunity. This article examines the development of the national value system in the process of preparing students for professional activities.*

Keywords: *education, values, social factor, direction, feature, Social values, educational values, dignity, pedagogue, educational processes, subject, provision, independent thinking.*

The orientation of educational values towards the social and personal factor is revealed. Social values, including educational ones, serve to shape a person, increase his value, ensure that teachers recognize the individual factor as the leading subject of the educational process, in which free and independent thinking, as well as the social, is desirable to help. develop activity skills. Therefore, the need to educate a competent individual and a qualified specialist for adult life acquires a more relevant meaning and essence in modern conditions, when new social relations are developing and consolidating. "Education of free, comprehensively developed people, aware of their rights, counting on their own strengths and capabilities, independently relating to the events taking place around them and at the same time building their personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country." and people. needed." And it depends on educational values. That is why he emphasizes the relevance of the chosen topic by teaching educational values to the youth.

One of the urgent tasks facing the educational process today is the use of national values and traditions in the education of a comprehensively developed personality. At the same time, in our country, the education of a mentally mature and mature person until adulthood has been elevated to the level of state policy. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Uzbekistan is always faithful to its traditions in the field of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance and will never deviate from this path. Today we believe in our multinational people, in our youth, who are our hope and support, and we are approaching the finish line. Thinking about the happiness and maturity of our dear children and grandchildren, counting on the bright future of our people, we set ourselves enormous tasks. I think it is appropriate to quote people with great intentions, their work will be great, their lives will be bright, and their future will be prosperous. It should be noted here that national values and traditions are of great importance in the process of education, and it would not be superfluous to say that they act as the most effective weapon in the process of education. [1.81]

We know that society cannot achieve its future without development or strengthening spiritual values in the minds of young people, and each country has its own destiny to educate the rising future generation on the basis of its national values, traditions and customs. the right to self-determination, that is, independence. Islam Karimov, First President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, said: “As we strive to build a legal, democratic and fair state, the main priority is to enhance the spirituality of our people, which embodies cultural and most sensitive feelings. , deep philosophical, political and legal concepts. has become one of the tasks” [2,306] - we are once again convinced that our goal is to raise an independent, free, educated, in a word, comprehensively developed person. Independence is an important condition for realizing this goal.

Pedagogical values are norms that act as a cognitive-acting system that regulates pedagogical activity and acts as a mediator and link between the existing social picture of the world in the field of education and the activities of the teacher. They, like other meanings, are syntagmatic in nature, i.e. is formed in a historical form and is fixed as a form of social consciousness in the form of specific images and ideas in the science of pedagogy. The acquisition of pedagogical values occurs in the course of pedagogical activity, during which their subjectivization occurs. The degree of subjectivity of these pedagogical values serves as an indicator of the personal and professional development of the teacher. Value is a concept that shows the positive or negative value of surrounding things, a person for society, which is a moral principle.

The value types are as follows:

- natural values;
- material values;
- spiritual values;

The values and tasks associated with their use in the process of organizing socio-pedagogical relations must be included in the basis for organizing relationships in the content of education, its process and the “teacher-student” system.

When modeling the educational process, in order to pedagogically correctly organize the life and activities of students in educational institutions, one should not forget about their effective attitude to external factors of influence. Research by teachers and psychologists shows that the mutual influence of external factors on a person (both negative and positive) primarily depends on the relationships between students. When organizing the educational activities of students, a teacher or educator needs to know what he gets from them, assessing the student’s attitude, experiences and understanding in relation to external influencing factors. When modeling the educational process, it is necessary to achieve growth not only in the mind, but also in the feelings of the student, during which moral skills and habits are formed in accordance with the moral requirements of society. To achieve this, you need the mind of a student. emotions and will influence.

The teacher must be able to organize forms of learning at an optimal level during the educational process, enrich the theory of the formation of a comprehensively developed personality with various new ideas. Currently, such didactic principles as “Knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation” are recognized as important categories for preparing a teacher’s pedagogical skills; mature public figures have been involved in this activity since ancient times. It is emphasized that the education of the younger generation and its organization are an important factor determining not only personal maturity, but also the development of society.

The teacher leads the educational process. It determines the educational activities of students in an educational institution, creates conditions for their active involvement in the social process and active participation in educational activities. Thanks to active participation in the

social process, students' independence and creative initiative increases. When modeling this activity, the teacher must take into account the interests and needs of the student body. When a child becomes responsible for his own behavior and behavior to the team. He is not a performer, but an active participant in the overall work. [3.201]

In conclusion, he cites the words of our grandfather Abdullah Avloni, who was active in the ranks of the national liberation movement: "Education is a matter of life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster." "[4.39] I found it acceptable to pass. Essentially, a child is a young sprout and grows in the direction in which it bends. The education given to our youth determines the future and destiny of our country.

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